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Effectively organizing the topic "How should we conserve natural resources?" in primary grades

Avazmetova Intizor Rajapboyevna

Associate Professor of the Department of Biology, Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhon Beruni

Abdusharipova Malohat Xudaynazar qizi

Teacher at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Yusupbayeva Shahrizoda Muzaffar qizi

Student at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Xudayberganova Gulzoda Dilmurod qizi

Student at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

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Annotation: This article discusses how to effectively convey knowledge about nature and natural resources to primary school students, teach them to preserve them, and organize this topic in the lesson process. Methods for forming an ecological culture in students using various methods, didactic games, experiments, and practical exercises are considered.

Keywords: natural resources, ecological education, primary education, teaching methodology, nature conservation, ecological awareness, practical exercises, interdisciplinary integration.

Introduction.

In the modern education system, environmental education and the formation of a careful attitude to nature play an important role. It is especially necessary to start this process from an early stage - from the primary grades, to give students a correct understanding of the importance of natural resources and the need to preserve them. Through the topic "How should we preserve natural resources?", students are instilled with ecological awareness, love for nature, and a sense of responsibility [1].

Natural resources are the resources created by nature and used by humans: water, air, land, minerals, forests, fauna and flora. They are very important for human life and are in danger of being depleted. It is effective to explain this concept to primary school students through simple, real-life examples [2].

Due to the increasing number of environmental problems in modern society, one of the main tasks of the education system is to form environmental awareness and ecological culture from childhood. In primary school, this process is carried out through the content of the lesson. In particular, through the topic "How should we preserve natural resources?", students understand the need to preserve nature and learn to have a conscious attitude towards nature [3].

For primary school students, it is necessary to explain these concepts through simple, interesting examples. For example: “If we waste water, we may not have enough drinking water in the future.”[4]

Photographs, videos, and models provide an idea of the types of natural resources, their conservation status, and pollution. This method attracts children’s attention and helps them remember the topic better.

Students conduct small experiments at school on planting trees and saving water;

Through the “waste sorting” practice, they learn to contribute to environmental cleanliness;

An observation notebook is kept on saving water.

Students play the roles of “ecologist,” “tree,” “water,” and “nature helping people” These games increase children’s social awareness and enliven the lesson.

Teaching a topic by linking it to the native language (reading poetry), visual arts (drawing a natural landscape), or labor lessons (making eco-items from paper) increases the effectiveness of the lesson.

Questions such as “What could be the reason for the water shortage in our school?” and “What will happen if trees are cut down?” help students develop their thinking, analysis, and problem-solving skills.

Student assessment and motivation

Awarding honorary certificates with nominations such as “Friend of Nature”, “Eco-Hero”;

Organizing mini-projects such as “Green Week”, “Protectors of Nature”;

Encouraging students who think independently and participate in eco-campaigns to deepen environmental awareness⁹.

The formation of environmental culture in primary school students, especially through the topic “How should we protect natural resources?” is successfully implemented using various teaching methods. Lessons are made interesting, effective, and close to life through visual aids, role-playing games, practical work, and interdisciplinary connections. This will form the basis for the formation of love, responsibility, and a conscious attitude towards nature in students.

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